

TRIAL TO OPTIMIZE FRACTURE PROPERTIES AND BIODEGRADABILITY IN HAP/PLA COMPOSITES AS BIO-ABSORBABLE BONE SUBSTITUTE USING HYBRID INTERFACE CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

Previously, we had proposed the hybrid interface control in HAp/PLA composite materials as one of the most promising candidates of scaffold materials for the bone regeneration, using both pectin and chitosan, in order to improve the interfacial bonding strength. Here, photo-dissociable protective groups, which can be eliminated from the protection site by the irradiation of ultraviolet rays, was applied into the carboxyl groups of pectin, in order to avoid the direct chemical reaction between pectin and chitosan. As results, we could hypothesize that the optimization of the interface-control ratio could bring the enough fracture properties and higher biodegradability to HAp/PLA. In this study, we tried to evaluate the effect of the interface-control ratio on the fracture properties of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites. As results, it is considered that 11 wt% of pectin and 0.6 wt% of chitosan can modify 100 % of surface of HAp particles. The tensile test results indicated that the tensile strength increased with increasing interface-control ratio. Thus, it can be summarized that the control of interface-control ratio, which is aimed in this study, was achieved successfully.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, biocompatible materials such as titanium alloys and calcium phosphates have been main currents as bone substitute materials for bone defects. However, by using these materials, the revision surgery is needed owing to their deterioration or metal-ion elution. In addition, these materials have much higher stiffness compared with living tissues. Thus, most of applied load is supported by substitute materials, resulting in bone resorption owing to the shortage of mechanical stimulation to surrounding bone. Therefore, biocompatible materials with fracture properties enough for substituting bone, stiffness equivalent to surrounding bone and biodegradability equivalent to bone formation speed had been demanded as scaffold materials for bone regeneration surgery of bone defects [1-4]. Biocompatible materials composed of poly-lactic-acid (PLA) matrix and bio-ceramic particles, such as hydroxyapatite (HAp) particles, are one of the most promising candidates for this application [5-13]. However, mainly the poor interfacial bonding between PLA and HAp caused low fracture properties of HAp/PLA composites, limiting their practical application [6, 8]. Thus, it is desired that the interfacial bonding strength would be improved using the method appropriate for material systems applied in living bodies.

Previously, we had improved the interfacial bonding of HAp/PLA composites by a surface treatment of HAp particles using natural-derived polymers (pectin: acidic polymer, chitosan: basic polymer) [14, 15]. However, it was impossible to modify the whole surface of HAp particles using chitosan or pectin separately, because we utilized the electrostatic interaction between HAp particles and modification polymers. Therefore, we had tried the "hybrid" interface-control of HAp particles using both chitosan and pectin, resulting in the successful improvement of fracture properties of

HAp/PLA composites [16, 17]. Here, the hydrolytic degradation rate in tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites was higher than that of neat PLA. This result suggests that unmodified surface was still remained on HAp particles after the hybrid interface-control. In addition, the hydrolytic degradation rate in tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites was higher than that of uncontrolled HAp/PLA composites, after long-term hydrolysis. This result suggests the acceleration of hydrolysis by the introduction of photo-dissociable protective groups, which were necessary to avoid the direct chemical reaction between chitosan and pectin. Therefore, we hypothesized that both fracture and hydrolysis properties could be improved by optimize the interface-control ratio, which can be defined by dividing the hybrid interface-controlled surface area by the whole surface area. In this study, we tried to evaluate the effect of the interface-control ratio on the fracture properties of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

In this study, PLA (Toray Industries, Inc., Ecodea 330-RC30, initial viscosity average molecular weight: 2×10^5) was used as matrix, and HAp particles (KDD, average diameter: 2 - 20 [μm]) was used as fillers. Pectin (Kanto Chemical Co. Inc., originated from citrus) and chitosan (Kanto Chemical Co. Inc., originated from crustacean) were used as modification polymers in consideration with the biological affinity. In addition, o-nitrobenzyl alcohol (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) was used as photo-dissociable protective groups, in order to protect the carboxyl ends of pectin from chitosan.

2.2 Preparation method of hybrid interface-controlled HAp particles

A schematic drawing of the hybrid-interface-control method is shown in Figure 1. First, HAp particles were dissolved into the pectin solution (solute: pectin, solvent: distilled water), followed by stirring at 30 °C and standing at room temperature. Pectin-modified HAp particles were prepared by drying of the obtained precipitation. Secondary, pectin-modified HAp particles and o-nitrobenzyl alcohol were dissolved into dichloromethane (Kanto Chemical Co., Inc., purity: 99.5 %) at room temperature, followed by stirring and standing. Protected pectin-modified HAp particles were prepared by drying the obtained precipitation. Then, protected pectin-modified HAp particles were dissolved into the chitosan solution (solute: chitosan, solvent: acetic acid (Kanto Chemical Co., Inc.)), followed by stirring at 30 °C and standing at room temperature. Protected hybrid-interface-controlled HAp particles were prepared by drying the obtained precipitation. Finally, the photo-dissociable protective groups were deprotected by the irradiation of ultraviolet rays (wave length: 365×10^{-9} m, irradiation time: 1800 s) for protected hybrid-interface-controlled HAp particles dissolved into dichloromethane.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of hybrid-interface-control for HAp surface.

2.3 Preparation method of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites

First, hybrid interface-controlled HAp particles (3.0 [g]) were dissolved into dichloromethane (85.5 [g]), followed by stirring. Then, PLA (12 [g]) was dissolved into dichloromethane suspension of HAp particles,

followed by stirring until PLA was completely dissolved. Obtained solution was poured into ethanol (150 [ml]), resulting in re-precipitation. Obtained precipitate was dried at room temperature for 24 h in a desiccator and then at 40 °C for 5 h in a thermostat oven, followed by cutting into small pieces. These pieces were melted at 180 °C for 15 min on a hot-pressing device (TechnoSupply Co., Ltd., G-12), as shown in Figure 2. Then, hot-pressing was conducted at 180 °C under pressure of 8 MPa for 3 min, followed by the rapid cooling. Thickness of prepared HAp/PLA composite films was nominally 0.5 mm. As the reference material, neat PLA was also prepared by the same hot-pressing process.

Figure 2: Hot-pressing set-up.

2.4 Evaluation method of interface-control ratio

In order to evaluate the interface-control ratio, R_m , the change in the height of absorption peaks was evaluated when the concentration of modification polymers was varied within the range of 0.4 [wt%] to 15 [wt%], using a Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR, Horiba, Ltd., FT-700). Here, the concentration of modification polymers, where the height of absorption peaks was maximum, was defined as the critical amount of modification polymers. Focused wave numbers were 1550 [cm^{-1}] and 1650 [cm^{-1}], corresponding to amino end groups in chitosan and carboxyl end groups in pectin.

2.5 Tensile test

In order to evaluate the effect of the interface-control ratio on the fracture properties, hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA specimens with varying interface-control ratio were prepared. Neat PLA specimen was also prepared as the reference material. The size of tensile specimens was 50 [mm] in length, 5 [mm] in width and 0.5 [mm] in nominal thickness. Tensile test was carried out using a table-top universal testing machine (Shimadzu, AGS-X) with a load cell of 500 N in capacity. The crosshead speed was 1.0 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Evaluation results of interface-control ratio

Figure 3 shows the change in the absorption peak height with increasing concentration of pectin. This indicates the absorption peak height of carboxyl groups increased with increasing concentration of pectin and saturated at the pectin concentration of 11 [wt%]. Thus, it was suggested that the critical amount of pectin is 11 [wt%]. Figure 4 shows the change in the absorption peak height with increasing concentration of chitosan. This indicates the absorption peak height of amino groups increased with increasing concentration of chitosan and saturated at the chitosan concentration of 0.6 [wt%]. Thus, it was suggested that the critical amount of chitosan is 0.6 [wt%]. From these results, we hypothesized that the hybrid interface-control using pectin of 11 [wt%] and chitosan of 0.6 [wt%] could modify the whole surface area of HAp particles. Here, this condition was defined as $R_m = 100$ [%].

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of pectin-modified HAp.

Figure 4: FT-IR spectra of chitosan-modified HAp.

3.2 Fracture properties

Figure 5 shows the typical stress-strain curves obtained by tensile tests. The tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites was not higher than that of neat PLA. Our previous work [16] indicated that the tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites scatters largely. In addition, the amount of photo-dissociable protective groups was not optimized in

this study. Thus, it is suggested that the reason why the tensile strength of neat PLA was higher than that of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites was the existence of unmodified surface area still on the HAp particles with R_m of 100 [%]. On the other hand, the tensile test results indicate that the tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites increased with increasing interface-control ratio, R_m . It is considered that the increase in the tensile strength can be attributed to the improvement of interfacial bonding by the increase of the interface-control ratio.

Figure 5: Typical stress-strain curves of neat PLA and hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLAs..

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we tried to evaluate the effect of the interface-control ratio on the fracture properties of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites. As results, it is considered that 11 wt% of pectin and 0.6 wt% of chitosan can modify 100 % of surface of HAp particles. The tensile test results indicate that the tensile strength of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites increased with increasing interface-control ratio. Thus, it can be summarized that the control of the interface-control ratio, which is aimed in this study, was achieved successfully. In future, the existence of unmodified surface area on the HAp particles and the optimization of the amount of photo-dissociable protective groups should be solved in order to avoid the scattering of fracture properties of hybrid interface-controlled HAp/PLA composites.

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